

Title: Performance Evaluation of the Clayton Bi-Directional Impeller Turbine for Oscillating Water Column Applications

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Abstract:

The Clayton Bi-Directional Impeller Turbine is a novel wave energy conversion technology developed to replace the Well's turbine in oscillating water column (OWC) applications. Unlike the Well's turbine, which has voids between its blades that allow air to pass through without contributing to energy generation—resulting in an estimated 35-65% loss—the Clayton turbine captures nearly all available airflow. The Clayton turbine maintains efficiency across a broader range, particularly at 5-6 m/s and 12+ m/s, where the Well's Turbine stalls. While the exact percentage of the world's beaches experiencing waves in the 5-6 meters per second (m/s) range is not readily available, global wave energy assessments indicate that many coastal regions do experience wave conditions within this spectrum. Bench testing revealed its efficiency across varying air and water flows, showing promise beyond OWC in Power Buoys, Point Absorbers, and Tidal. Additionally, it may benefit overtopping devices for shoreline protection, floating platforms, conduit surge protection, and fluid pumping.

Bench-scale testing simulated wave-driven airflow conditions, comparing the Clayton turbine's performance against the Well's turbine. Results showed greater rotational stability and energy conversion efficiency across diverse flow conditions. A Halbach array enhances magnetic flux and acts as a flywheel, which increases rotational inertia and smooths power output. Further research explores serpentine coil configurations for space-saving electrical generation. Unlike the Well's turbine, the Clayton turbine is self-starting and does not require an external motor.

It quickly adapts to changing wave conditions, and with no flaps or valves, its only moving part is the rotor shaft combination, enhancing

durability while minimizing costs and maintenance. Unlike the Well's turbine, which has empty voids between propeller blades leading to energy loss, the Clayton turbine ensures all airflow contributes to rotation.

The turbine's ability to maintain rotation through rapid oscillations makes it particularly suited for near-shore environments where waves reflect off rocky coastlines, creating high-frequency flow reversals. The flywheel effect from the Halbach array helps sustain power generation even in turbulent conditions, ensuring stable energy conversion in both air and water applications.

Future efforts include computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modeling via SimScale to analyze airflow and optimize performance. Planned open-water testing at PacWave, a dedicated wave energy converter (WEC) test site, will validate analytical models and assess real-world viability.

This research advances marine energy technology by offering an alternative to propeller turbine designs, improving wave energy conversion. We hope to bring our bench testing model for active demonstration along with our Poster.

The Clayton Bi-Directional Impeller Turbine has received Letters of Support from Oregon State University's Hinsdale Wave Research Laboratory, the Small Business Administration (SBA), and the Southern Oregon Economic Development District (SOEDD), underscoring its potential for marine energy applications.

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